

Biological Foundations Heredity, Prenatal Development, and Birth

Sickle cell Disease Inheritance

Sickle cell anemia is a disease in which the body produces crescent-shaped red blood cells or sickles. The cells do not last long as the normal ones, which results in a low number of red blood cells(anaemia). The sickle cells also get stuck in blood vessels and block blood flow, which also carries white blood cells. The affected exhibit symptoms such as anemia repeated infections, and periodic pain episodes called crises. The condition is brought about by changes in the HBB gene and is inherited in an autosomal recessive pattern. Autosomal inheritance means the genes are located in the somatic genes (non-sex chromosomes). The sickle cell gene is a recessive gene implying that both copies of the responsible gene must have a disease-causing change for a person to have the disease. An individual with an autosomal recessive disease receives a gene with a pathogenic variant from each parent, with each parent being a carrier. When two carriers of the autosomal recessive disease have a child, they have a 1 in 4 chance of having a child with sickle cell disease.

Genes come in pairs, each set from the mother and the other from the father. To be born with sickle cell disease, one must inherit a copy of the sickle cell gene from both parents. This change happens when both parents are carriers of the sickle cell gene, also referred to as having the sickle cell trait. It can also happen when one parent has a sickle cell disease, and the other parent has the sickle cell trait. Sickle cell carriers show no visible symptoms nor experience the severe effects of the disease, but there is a chance their children could have sickle cell disease.

If both Leslie and Glen are sickle cell carriers, there is a 1 in 4 chance each child will not inherit any sickle cell gene and, therefore, will not have the sickle cell disease nor be able to pass it on to the successive generation. If only Leslie is a carrier, there is a 1 in 2 chance

that each child they will have will inherit a copy of the sickle cell gene and be a carrier. Furthermore, there is a 1 in 4 chance that each child they will have will inherit copies of the sickle cell gene from both parents and will be born with the disease. On the other hand, Leslie might not be a carrier after all and needs to undergo the following tests to ascertain her fears and suspicions.

Reproductive health research has, over the decades, ensured a better understanding of the genetic risk factors as a crucial part of reproductive options understanding for planning. With the help of Expanded Carrier Screening (ECS), carrier status information is obtained during the preconception period, which has helped assess appropriate reproductive options. Further, Preimplantation Genetic Testing (PGT) helps obtain genetic information for embryo prioritization. Aneuploidy (PGT-A) and gene variant (PGT-M) tests can simultaneously increase the probability of successful pregnancies and healthier future generations. Additionally, in the case of ongoing Gestation, prenatal genetic testing helps acquire information on foetal health.

From Conception to Birth

Prenatal development is divided into three main stages, Germinal, Embryonic and Foetal. The prenatal stage remains an essential part of a child's development process. It is a time when remarkable change helps set the stage for future psychological development. The brain develops during this period but will grow further during the early childhood years (Bailey and Emmerson, 2018). The prenatal development process occurs in three main stages: germinal, embryonic and foetal. The germinal stage occurs in the first two weeks after conception. The embryonic period lasts from the third to the eighth week, while the foetal period occurs between the ninth week and birth.

The germinal stage starts at conception when the sperm and the egg unite and fertilize from a zygote. The single-celled zygote journeys down from the fallopian tube to the uterus. Cell division occurs between the 24 to 36 hours after conception through mitosis, with the zygote first dividing into two, four, eight, and sixteen cells. The cell begins to differentiate after the eight-cell point is reached. cell division continues rapidly and develops into a blastocyst of three layers, each developing into different body structures. The ectoderm develops into the skin and the nervous system; the endoderm develops into the digestive and respiratory systems, as the mesoderm develops into the muscle and skeletal systems. The blastocyst arrives at the uterus and is attached to the uterine wall through implantation. Successful implantation causes hormonal changes that stop the normal menstrual cycle and bring about various physical changes. At this stage, smoking and drinking alcohol and coffee should be avoided or reduced to protect the growing foetus.

The Embryonic stage starts in the third week by forming mass cells called the embryo, which becomes distinct as a human. In the fourth week, the neural tube is formed, which later develops into the central nervous system, including the brain and the spinal cord. The neural plate also forms during this time with the emergence of two and later more ridges along each side of the neural plate to form a hollow tube. The brain vesicles form and develop into parts of the brain, including the forebrain, midbrain and hindbrain. The head begins to form in the fourth week, with eyes, nose, ears and mouth following quickly. The heart starts to develop with the pulsing of the blood vessels. The arms and legs appear in the fifth week. All the essential organs and parts except the sex organs are intact by the eight weeks, with the embryo weighing just one gram and measuring about an inch in length. By the end of the period, the primary brain and central nervous system have been formed together with a defined peripheral nervous system.

The foetal stage starts with the completion of cell differentiation. The brain undergoes many vital changes at this stage, which begins during the ninth week and lasts until birth. The early body systems and structures are fully established in this stage. The neural tube develops into the brain, the spinal cord and neurons form and migrate to the correct locations, and synapses and the connections between the neurons begin to develop. The period between the ninth and twelfth week marks the emergence of reflexes, and the foetus begins to make reflexive motions with its arms and legs.

The sex organs begin to form during the third month, and all body parts are fully formed by the start of the fourth month. By the start of the fourth month, fingernails, hair, eyelashes and toenails start to form. The brain and the nervous system become more responsive during this period. The brain starts to mature with activities resembling those of a sleeping newborn. Between the seventh month and birth, the foetus continues to develop, add weight, and prepare for outdoor life as the lungs expand and contract, preparing for breathing.

Prenatal development influences

The use of cell phones during pregnancy has not been proven to affect pregnancy in any way known to obstetricians and gynaecologists. However, since the energy emitted by cell phones, which is between the extremes of x-rays and granite, researchers have raised concerns about its ability to affect the growing baby in the uterus, whose cells are fast replicating and are vulnerable to outside disturbances. Nevertheless, a few studies in this field have not found any concerning issues with the use of phones. To ease worries, Chloe is advised to keep her phone a few feet away when not using and use hands-free devices (Pelz and Overstreet, 2002).

All alcohol consumption harms pregnancy since the mother passes alcohol to the baby through the umbilical cord and can cause miscarriage, stillbirth, and lifelong physical,

behavioral, and intellectual disabilities, including alcohol spectrum disorders (FASD). There is no known safe amount of alcohol use during pregnancy. All types of alcohol are equally harmful and should be avoided during pregnancy.

The mother's age does not directly affect the child's mental state, as every case is unique. However, a child's mental state is affected by factors such as nutrition, environmental hazards, exposure to the mother, and diseases. The mother's age remains a myth not rooted in evidence as a factor affecting a child's brain development.

References

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